

HEALTH BEHIND BARS: QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF BASIC AND HEALTH NEEDS OF PERSONS DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the health behind bars: a quantitative assessment of basic and health needs of individuals deprived of liberty in Zamboanga del Norte Correctional and Rehabilitation Center this calendar year, 2024. Further, this study used descriptive quantitative research method, using an adapted and modified questionnaire as its principal tool of gathering data. It was found out the majority of the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) were adults, specifically within the age range of 28–37 years old, and most were males and high school graduates. These findings indicate that the incarcerated population in the studied facility is largely composed of educated adult males. The results also revealed that the implementation of programs addressing the basic and health needs of PDLs was “very much implemented.” Among the basic needs, the availability of toiletries and the provision of nutritious food were the most evident, while in terms of health needs, personal hygiene practices and environmental sanitation were prioritized. Furthermore, the findings showed no significant difference in the respondents’ perceptions of program implementation when grouped according to age, sex, and educational attainment. This suggests that correctional programs were carried out uniformly and equitably, ensuring that all PDLs, regardless of demographic background, experienced similar access and quality of services. The results affirm that institutional management practices, such as equal provision of basic and health-related interventions, contribute to consistent satisfaction and welfare among inmates.

Keywords: *persons deprived of liberty, basic needs, health needs, jail, correction and rehabilitation facility*

INTRODUCTION

Jail serves a crucial function in the criminal justice system as an isolation tool that separates offenders from society, aligning with the constitutional rights of citizens to live in a safe environment. In a democratic society, all individuals, including the accused, are entitled to correction and rehabilitation, recognizing the need to address socially unacceptable behavior. In the Philippines, the corrections system involves cooperation among government, civil society, and business sectors for the confinement and rehabilitation of those charged with crimes. Jails and prisons are not just punitive facilities; they are designed for reform, education, and moral recovery. Unfortunately, the general public often overlooks prisoners, neglecting their potential return to society (Caño et al., 2024).

The negative consequences of imprisonment extend beyond the mere loss of physical liberty, impacting various facets of an individual's optimal functioning. The true suffering arises from frustrations and privations linked to the loss of freedom, including the lack of heterosexual relationships, social segregation, and the withholding of commodities and services. These short-term disappointments, manifested as missed opportunities, discomfort, boredom, and loneliness, exacerbate the anguish by threatening the offender's identity and self-worth. As a result, offenders often experience a diminished perception of themselves as valuable individuals, alongside the loss of societal respect, citizenship standing, and personal belongings, all of which significantly affect their self-identity. Such a condition may be detrimental to the PDL's health and wellness (De Vera et al., 2022).

The jail personnel are making efforts to enhance the professionalism of jail services while ensuring that Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) receive essential needs such as food, medicine, and rehabilitation supplies. However, self-harming behavior among PDLs has emerged as a significant health issue, attributed to various stressors experienced in custody. Thus, food is a core concern for jail administrators, emphasizing its direct connection to inmate health, welfare, discipline, and morale, ultimately impacting jail control and security management. Furthermore, jails conduct necessary medical and physical examinations of inmates upon their admission and provide treatment for illnesses during confinement. Psychiatric and psychological evaluations and treatments are also required, along with provisions for medications and hospitalization for severely ill prisoners. Furthermore, dental care should address inmates' dental issues, offering preventive services where applicable. Jail management has implemented numerous recreational activities to promote inmate well-being, and it is crucial to monitor their effectiveness in relation to the inmate population (Agustin et al., 2024).

The Zamboanga del Norte Correctional and Rehabilitation Center, a provincial jail, is experiencing challenges in managing inmates due to the large number of detainees,

which may affect their services and deprive the inmates of their rights. In this connection, researchers have their rights. Researchers decided to conduct a study to investigate the most affected and implemented welfare and development programs among inmates. The result of the study helps frame possible recommendations to the rights of the person deprived of liberty. Thus, this study aimed to determine the health behind bars: a quantitative assessment of basic and health needs of individuals deprived of liberty in Zamboanga del Norte Correctional and Rehabilitation Center this calendar year, 2024. The findings will give an update on the current state of health services available to individuals deprived of liberty (PDL) and highlight areas where improvements are necessary. By identifying gaps in care and support, the study aims to advocate for policies that uphold the dignity and rights of inmates, ensuring they receive adequate health services while incarcerated.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the health behind bars: a quantitative assessment of basic and health needs of individuals deprived of liberty in Zamboanga del Norte Correctional and Rehabilitation Center this calendar year, 2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex; and
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment?
2. What is the extent of the implementation of the programs for persons deprived of liberty, as to:
 - 2.1 Basic Needs; and
 - 2.2 Health Needs?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the implementations of programs for persons deprived of liberty when analyzed according to their profile?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research method, using an adapted and modified questionnaire based on the work of Bocar et al. (2018). Further, this study was conducted at the Zamboanga del Norte Correctional and Rehabilitation Center (Zamboanga del Norte Provincial Jail), situated at Don Jose Aquirre, Manukan, Zamboanga del Norte. Additionally, the study purposively selected fifty (50) persons deprived of liberty based on the following inclusion criteria: (a) having been a detainee in the aforementioned facility for at least one (1) year, (b) voluntarily agreeing to participate as respondents in this study, and (c) being able to comprehend and answer the questionnaire truthfully. The warden of the facility approved this study.

It is important to emphasize that the adapted-modified questionnaire had undergone a test of reliability, and it yielded a Cronbach Alpha Value of 0.8255, rendering the instrument highly reliable for use. Also, the questionnaire used a Likert 4-Scale, with 4 as Very Much Implemented, 3 as Much Implemented, 2 as Implemented, and 1 as Not Implemented.

Furthermore, the researchers personally administered the questionnaire and collected it after the respondents had completed their answers. The retrieved questionnaires were tallied and calculated statistically. Thus, this study used frequency count and percentage computation, weighted mean, Kruskal-Wallis H-test, and Mann-Whitney U-test as the statistical formulas used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the responses of the fifty (50) purposively selected persons deprived of liberty in Zamboanga del Norte Correctional and Rehabilitation Center (Zamboanga del Norte Provincial Jail). The responses were treated statistically to answer the research questions of the present investigation.

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The table revealed that the majority of the respondents were within the age range of 28–37 years old, comprising 25 out of 50 respondents, or 50.00%, followed by those respondents who were within the age range of 18–27 years old, comprising 11 out of 50 respondents, or 22.00%, as compared to a respondent who was within the age range of 58 years old and above, comprising 1 out of 50 respondents, or 2.00%. The table revealed that most of the respondents were within the age range of 28–37 years old, which implies that most of the persons deprived of liberty were adults. In support, Martinez and Buan (2025) and Guadamo (2020) aver the fact that the majority of persons deprived of liberty (PDLs) are adults, particularly within the age range of 28 to 37 years. It underscores the prevalence of adults, particularly those aged 28 to 37, among the incarcerated population in the Philippines.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
18 – 27 years old	11	22.00
28 – 37 years old	25	50.00
38 – 47 years old	9	18.00
48 – 57 years old	4	8.00
58 years old and above	1	2.00
Total	50	100.0

Table 2 displays the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. The table pointed out that most of the respondents were males, comprising 45 out of 50 respondents, or 90.00%, as compared to those male respondents comprising 5 out of 50 respondents, or 10.00%, which implies that most of the persons deprived of liberty were males. In support, Gales et al. (2023) stress the fact that males consistently outnumber females in incarceration rates.

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Female	5	10.00
Male	45	90.00
Total	50	100.0

Table 3 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment. The table revealed that most respondents were high school graduates, accounting for 35 out of 50 respondents, or 70.00%. This was followed by elementary graduates, who made up 9 out of 50 respondents, or 18.00%, and college graduates, who comprised 6 out of 50 respondents, or 12.00%. The findings stressed that most of the respondents were high school level/graduates, which implies that most of the persons deprived of liberty were educated. In support, Labarrete and Tiopes (2025) and Sagge et al. (2023) pointed out that a significant number of PDLs in the Philippines are educated and actively seek opportunities for further learning and personal development. Furthermore, these individuals possessed literacy and numeracy skills and expressed interest in further education, including entrepreneurial and livelihood training.

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Elementary Level/Graduate	9	18.00
High School Level/Graduate	35	70.00
Senior High School Level/Graduate	-	-
College Level	6	12.00
Bachelor's Degree Holder	-	-
Total	50	100.0

Table 4. Extent of the Implementation of the Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty as to Basic Needs

Extent of the Implementation of the Programs for Persons' Deprived of Liberty as to Basic Needs	AWV	Interpretation
1. Provision of nutritious food.	3.44	Very Much Implemented
2. Provision of potable drinking water.	3.16	Much Implemented
3. Well-maintained accommodation (light, ventilation, water).	3.42	Very Much Implemented
4. Comfortable sleeping quarters.	3.32	Very Much Implemented
5. Availability of Toiletries (soap, shampoo, toothbrush).	3.58	Very Much Implemented
Mean	3.384	Very Much Implemented

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Not Implemented; 1.76 – 2.50 Implemented; 2.51 – 3.25 Much Implemented; 3.26 – 4.00 Very Much Implemented

Table 4 displays the extent of the implementation of the programs for persons deprived of liberty as to basic needs. The table revealed that most of the respondents viewed the availability of toiletries as very much implemented, having an average weighted value of 3.58, followed by the provisions of nutritious food as very much implemented, having an average weighted value of 3.44. The mean on this aspect is 3.384, verbally interpreted as "very much implemented." The findings stressed that most of the respondents were very much impressed with the availability of toiletries, which implies that the implementation of programs for PDLs as to basic needs connotes the availability of toiletries. In support, De Vera et al. (2022) and Lim and Parreño (2020) pointed out that the implementation of programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) includes the provision of toiletries as part of their basic needs. Furthermore, the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) and the Bureau of Corrections (BuCor) explicitly list hygiene kits, such as soap, toothpaste, and towels, as essential supplies for PDLs.

Table 5. Extent of the Implementation of the Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty as to Health Needs

Extent of the Implementation of the Programs for Persons' Deprived of Liberty as to Health Needs	AWV	Interpretation
1. Personal Hygiene Practices	3.50	Very Much Implemented
2. Availability of medical treatment.	3.28	Very Much Implemented
3. Availability of dental treatment.	3.10	Much Implemented
4. Availability of medicine/medical supplies.	3.16	Much Implemented
5. Availability of medical/dental facilities and equipment.	3.10	Much Implemented
6. Health education lessons.	3.05	Much Implemented
7. No smoking policy.	3.30	Very Much Implemented
8. No alcoholic beverages policy.	3.20	Much Implemented

9. Separation of infectious-disease-infected inmates.	3.45	Very Much Implemented
10. Environmental Sanitation.	3.48	Very Much Implemented
Mean	3.262	Very Much Implemented

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Not Implemented; 1.76 – 2.50 Implemented; 2.51 – 3.25 Much Implemented; 3.26 – 4.00 Very Much Implemented

Table 5 displays the extent of the implementation of the programs for persons deprived of liberty with regard to their health needs. The table revealed that most of the respondents viewed personal hygiene practices as very much implemented, having an average weighted value of 3.50, followed by environmental sanitation as very much implemented, having an average weighted value of 3.48. The mean on this aspect is 3.262, verbally interpreted as "very much implemented." The findings stressed that most of the respondents viewed it as very much implemented on personal hygiene practices, which implies that the implementation of the programs for persons deprived of liberty as to health needs connotes implementation on personal hygiene practices. In support, Macasu et al. (2025) and Hanafi (2024) pointed out that the implementation of health programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) includes promoting personal hygiene practices. The Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) provides hygiene kits and conducts wellness activities emphasizing cleanliness and sanitation as part of its health initiatives. These efforts aim to prevent illnesses and maintain the overall well-being of PDLs.

Table 6. Test of Difference on the Extent of Implementation of the Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty as to Basic Needs when Analyzed According to the Profile of the Respondents

Factors Compared	Extent of Implementation of the Programs for Persons' Deprived of Liberty as to Basic Needs				
Profile	H-value	U-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	11.7038		0.4266	No Significant Difference	H ₀ was accepted
Sex		234	0.1223	No Significant Difference	H ₀ was accepted
Educational Attainment	17.2754		0.3561	No Significant Difference	H ₀ was accepted

*p-value < 0.05 level of significance = significant; Reject H₀

**p-value > 0.05 level of significance = not significant; Fail to Reject H₀

Table 6 presents the differences in the extent of implementation of programs for persons deprived of liberty regarding basic needs, analyzed based on the respondents' profiles. Applying the Mann-Whitney U-test and Kruskal-Wallis H-test, it yields a p-value greater than the level of significance set at 0.05, which implies acceptance of the

hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the extent of implementation of the programs for persons deprived of liberty as to basic needs when analyzed according to the profile of the respondents. Thus, young and old, male and female, as well as highly and lowly educated, had the same view on the extent of implementation of the programs for persons deprived of liberty as to basic needs. In support, Labarrete and Tiopes (2025) and Bersamina et al. (2023) support the finding that demographic characteristics such as age, sex, and educational attainment do not significantly influence the perceptions of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) regarding jail programs and services. Further, it was found that PDLs, regardless of their background, shared similar views about the adequacy and implementation of basic needs programs, emphasizing that institutional management and equal access to services contribute to uniform experiences among inmates.

Table 7. Test of Difference on the Extent of Implementation of the Programs for Persons' Deprived of Liberty as to Health Needs when Analyzed According to the Profile of the Respondents

Factors Compared		Extent of Implementation of the Programs for Persons' Deprived of Liberty as to Health Needs			
Profile	H-value	U-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	11.9038		0.5261	No Significant Difference	H ₀ was accepted
Sex		225	0.4223	No Significant Difference	H ₀ was accepted
Educational Attainment	11.2754		0.3561	No Significant Difference	H ₀ was accepted

*p-value < 0.05 level of significance = significant; Reject H₀

**p-value > 0.05 level of significance = not significant; Fail to Reject H₀

Table 7 presents the differences in the extent of implementation of programs for persons deprived of liberty regarding health needs, analyzed based on the respondents' profiles. The application of the Mann-Whitney U-test and Kruskal-Wallis H-test yields a p-value greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicating acceptance of the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the extent of program implementation for persons deprived of liberty regarding health needs when analyzed by respondents' profiles. Thus, individuals of all ages, genders, and education levels shared the same perspective on the extent of implementation of health programs for persons deprived of liberty. In support, Macasu et al. (2025) and Martinez and Buan (2025) revealed that demographic factors such as age, sex, and educational attainment did not significantly affect the level of satisfaction of PDLs regarding healthcare services. This suggests that health programs and services within prisons are generally implemented uniformly, providing equal access and treatment to all inmates regardless of their background.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the majority of the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) were adults, specifically within the age range of 28–37 years old, and most were males and high school graduates. These findings indicate that the incarcerated population in the studied facility is largely composed of educated adult males. The results also revealed that the implementation of programs addressing the basic and health needs of PDLs was “very much implemented.” Among the basic needs, the availability of toiletries and the provision of nutritious food were the most evident, while in terms of health needs, personal hygiene practices and environmental sanitation were prioritized.

Furthermore, the findings showed no significant difference in the respondents’ perceptions of program implementation when grouped according to age, sex, and educational attainment. This suggests that correctional programs were carried out uniformly and equitably, ensuring that all PDLs, regardless of demographic background, experienced similar access and quality of services. The results affirm that institutional management practices, such as equal provision of basic and health-related interventions, contribute to consistent satisfaction and welfare among inmates.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were offered:

The jail management should continue prioritizing personal hygiene and sanitation programs while ensuring regular medical and dental checkups to maintain inmates’ overall well-being.

The jail administrators should sustain the consistent availability of basic necessities such as toiletries, nutritious food, and potable water, and improve monitoring systems to prevent shortages or inequitable distribution.

The correctional facilities should maintain fair and inclusive access to all programs and services, ensuring that no PDL is disadvantaged regardless of age, sex, or educational background.

Institutional authorities should periodically assess the effectiveness of implemented programs related to basic and health needs to identify areas for improvement and align them with current national correctional standards and human rights policies.

Future researchers were encouraged to benchmark the result of the herein study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured the anonymity of the research participants and confirmed that consent was freely given for data collection related to this study. All information were stored securely and was destroyed after the study was completed. Confidentiality was strictly maintained.

Additionally, the researchers strictly avoided plagiarism and ensured that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results of this study were used solely for research purposes, adhering to the highest standards of academic integrity. Further, the researchers utilized the use of an AI software for grammar checking and paraphrasing.

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